

Leveraging Large Language Models for Building Interpretable Rule-Based Data-to-Text Systems

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Abstract

We introduce a simple approach that uses a large language model (LLM) to automatically implement a fully interpretable rule-based data-to-text system in pure Python. Experimental evaluation on the WebNLG dataset showed that such a constructed system produces text of better quality (according to the BLEU and BLEURT metrics) than the same LLM prompted to directly produce outputs, and produces fewer hallucinations than a BART language model fine-tuned on the same data. Furthermore, at runtime, the approach generates text in a fraction of the processing time required by neural approaches, using only a single CPU.

1 Introduction

Data-to-text is a field of natural language generation (NLG) that focuses on converting structured, non-linguistic data into coherent text (Gatt and Krahmer, 2018). This paper, like many others in the field (Castro Ferreira et al., 2020; Agarwal et al., 2021; Kasner and Dusek, 2022), specifically addresses the challenge of generating text from data expressed as RDF triples that consist of a subject, a predicate, and an object. For instance, one possible textualization of the following RDF triples: (Mozart, birthplace, Vienna), (Mozart, birth year, 1756) is “Mozart was born in 1756 in Vienna.”

There are two main approaches to the construction of data-to-text systems: rule-based and neural methods (Gatt and Krahmer, 2018). Rule-based approaches (Lavoie and Rainbow, 1997; White and Baldridge, 2003) rely on predefined templates and linguistic rules to transform structured data into text, ensuring high precision and control over the output. On the other hand, neural approaches leverage deep learning models to automatically learn the mapping from data to text (Ke et al., 2021; Chen et al., 2020). They offer greater flexibility and produce more natural and varied text, but have limited

interpretability, are more computationally intensive and prone to producing hallucinations (Rebuffel et al., 2022; Ji et al., 2023).

This paper combines these two perspectives on building NLG systems and proposes to use a large neural language model to *train* (implement) a rule-based system. Specifically, we propose a training procedure that processes the training set by asking a large language model to write simple Python code that would generate the reference text based on the input data. The generated code is executed to check for syntax errors and whether it produces the correct output. The final result of the training of the system is a single file of Python code that is able to generate a textualisation for the input data.

Although experimental evaluation on the WebNLG dataset (Gardent et al., 2017) showed that our automatically written rule-based system does not achieve the performance of a fully fine-tuned neural model in terms of BLEU or BLEURT score, it produces significantly fewer hallucinations and outperforms a non-trivial neural baseline on these measures. Moreover, our system is fully interpretable and offers high controllability, as it can be modified by a Python programmer if necessary. Our approach also does not require a GPU during inference and produces text almost instantaneously on a single CPU.

2 Target rule-based system structure

We conceptualize a high-level fixed structure for our proposed system’s Python code which organises processing according to the set of predicates present in the input triples. It contains two main elements: (1) an (initially empty) *list of rules* capable of converting a set of triples with particular predicates into text, and (2) a *rule selector* that processes the input triples and executes the corresponding rules.

Figure 1: An overview of the training process of our rule-based system. Note that the output of the training process is a NLG system implemented in pure Python code that does not need access to the LLM to generate text.

Each rule is a plain Python code snippet/subroutine, coupled with with simplistic specifications of the expected input, including the expected number of triples and the list of their expected predicates. The rules are arranged in a simple list. Before a rule’s code is executed, the input triples are always sorted to match the order of the predicates given in the rule’s specification. This allows simpler rules to be written and limits the number of potential errors.

The rule selector processes the input triples by extracting their predicates and executing the rule that has the same list of predicates in the specification. If there is no matching rule, the input is split into several parts by a splitting mechanism that aims to minimize the number of splits by applying greedy search. It iteratively searches for a rule capable of processing the largest subset of input triples, executes it, eliminates the already processed triples from the input and repeats the process. If no rule can be found by further splitting, the triples are converted to text by a default rule “{subject} {predicate} {object}”.

3 Training: LLM-based rule generation

The goal of the training procedure is to populate the list of rules with useful rules capable of producing a fluent and hallucination-free description of the input triples.

First, the approach makes a single pass through the training set, writing for each training example a Python code capable of producing the reference text (Sec. 3.1). The training procedure only analyses instances that are not fully covered by already trained rules (i.e. they cannot be processed without applying the splitting mechanism), which significantly reduces the size of the training set effectively

needed to train the system.

Next, the approach uses a simple mechanism to improve the generalisability of the constructed system (Sec. 3.2). The triples from the training set are clustered to discover sets of predicates that are likely to occur together on the input. Then, for each likely set of predicates, an artificial training example is constructed by interacting with an LLM, and then a standard rule construction procedure is applied.

3.1 Generating rules from training examples

The procedure for constructing a single rule for a given training instance consists of the three following steps:

Step 1: Prompt the LLM to write a rule The LLM is instructed to generate Python code that produces a factual textual description of the data given in the input. Both the triples and the expected output (reference text) are provided in the prompt, but the model is informed that the code should be general enough to produce correct text even if the subjects/objects given in the triples are changed. A simple code snippet is also included in the prompt to inform the model about the classes used to represent the input and the general structure of the code. See the full prompt in Appendix A.

Step 2: Execute and test the rule The code of the rule is extracted from the response provided by the LLM, and simple formatting heuristics are applied to correct minor issues such as incorrect code indentation. The code is then executed in a separate process with a predefined timeout. If the code terminates before the timeout, does not throw an error, and the Levenshtein distance between the output text and the reference is within a predefined range, the rule is considered correct and added to

the list of rules. Otherwise, the rule is regarded as incorrect.

Step 3: Correct the rule if needed If the rule written by the LLM is incorrect, the model is informed about the incorrect output produced or the error returned, and it is asked to correct the issue (see the prompt in Appendix A). This process is repeated twice. If the returned code is still incorrect, the generation process is restarted from scratch, beginning a new conversation with the model to write the rule (Step 1). If this procedure fails a second time, rule construction is skipped for the given training instance.

3.2 Generating additional rules for improved generalization

As mentioned above, we generate additional rules for predicates that are likely to occur together in a sentence to improve the generalisation of the constructed rule-based system.

Clustering predicates To cluster predicates from the training set, we have developed a simple graph clustering algorithm. We start by constructing a graph, where each node represents a predicate in the training set. We then add connections between nodes (predicates) that co-occur in at least one training instance. Each connected component in such a constructed graph represents an initial cluster of predicates.

Since some clusters are too large for further processing, we split connected components with more than 20 nodes by systematically removing nodes connected to all other nodes within the component. After adjusting the cluster sizes, we generate training instances for all pairs, triples and quadruples of predicates belonging to the same cluster using the procedure described below.

Generating synthetic training examples To create a training instance for a given list of predicates, we again prompt the LLM. The prompt includes an instruction to generate a full list of triples using the specified predicates (i.e., come up with some relevant subjects and objects for the predicates), along with a corresponding reference text. Several input-output examples from the training set are provided to the LLM for context. The number of these training examples varies to ensure coverage of all requested predicate textualisations. Specifically, we used the splitting procedure from the rule selector (see Sec. 2) to divide the list of predicates,

and then identified the relevant training examples for each part. The template for the corresponding LLM prompt can be found in Appendix A.

4 Experimental evaluation

4.1 Experimental setup

Dataset We performed experiments on the WebNLG benchmark (Gardent et al., 2017) containing data expressed as RDF triples and corresponding text references, which is prominent in many previous works. The rule-based system was trained only on the training part of the dataset, the fine-tuned baseline additionally used the development part as a validation set. All systems were tested on the in-domain part of the test set.

Baselines We compare the results of our rule-based approach with two baselines:

- The BART-base model (Lewis et al., 2020) fine-tuned on WebNLG dataset with the default architecture for conditional language modelling provided by HuggingFace library (Wolf et al., 2020). More training details are in Appendix B.
- A prompted LLM – to generate textual descriptions for provided triples, we use the instruction-tuned 70B version of the Llama 3 model (Touvron et al., 2023; Llama Team, 2024), in a quantized version through the *ollama* library.¹ A simple post-processing of the results was applied to remove superfluous text, such as encouragements for further interaction with the model. The prompt used is provided in Appendix A.

Our rule-based approach We run our procedure of training a rule-based approach with Llama 3 70B large language model. The threshold of 5 on the Levenshtein distance is used to verify the correctness of a rule during training (see Sec. 3.1, step 2). Training was performed on two NVidia L40 48GB GPUs with quantized models (FP8). The processing of the original WebNLG dataset took less than 7 hours (6h 56m) and resulted in the construction of 3,408 rules. The generation of additional rules (Sec. 3.2) resulted in approximately 110k new rules.

¹<https://ollama.com/>, model ID llama3:70b.

	BLEU	METEOR	BLEURT	inference time		interpretability
				GPU	CPU	
Prompted Llama 3 70B	38.26	0.680	0.113	6,360 s	n/a	×
Fine-tuned BART	53.28	0.716	0.257	249 s	1,910 s	×
Our rule-based approach (with Llama 3 70B)	<u>42.51</u>	0.671	<u>0.157</u>	-	3 s	✓

Table 1: Results of automatic evaluation on the WebNLG test set using BLEU, METEOR and BLEURT. Additionally, the inference time (in seconds) for the full test set is reported. The reported times do not include loading the models into memory and were measured on a machine with an Nvidia A40 48 GB GPU and an AMD EPYC 7313 CPU.

	hallucinations		omissions	disfluencies	repetitions
	minor	major			
Prompted Llama 3 70B	0.08	0.07	0.07	0.19	0.03
Fine-tuned BART	0.20	0.33	0.19	<u>0.16</u>	0.07
Our rule-based approach (with Llama 3 70B)	0.04	<u>0.13</u>	<u>0.08</u>	0.13	0.03

Table 2: Results of manual evaluation on a sample of 75 examples from the WebNLG test set (percentage of examples with different types of errors, see Sec. 4.3 for details).

4.2 Automatic evaluation

We investigate the quality of generated output using several popular metrics: BLEU (Papineni et al., 2002), METEOR (Banerjee and Lavie, 2005) and BLEURT (Sellam et al., 2020). Implementations of these metrics from HuggingFace (Wolf et al., 2020) are used. The results are presented in Table 1.

In terms of automatic text quality metrics, the fine-tuned BART model achieved the highest scores. However, our rule-based approach ranked second in both the BLEU and BLEURT metrics, outperforming the prompted Llama 3 model. Moreover, this result was computed on a single CPU 83 times faster than the fastest neural approach (BART) running on a GPU. We also assessed the effect of the additional rules generated from synthetic data by evaluated a variant of the system without these rules. We found the effect on metrics to be minimal (BLEU gain of 0.3%, BLEURT and METEOR stay within 0.001). Nevertheless, we still retain these rules to increase fluency for predicate combinations unseen in training data.

Experiments with different LLMs To investigate the impact of a particular selection of large language model, we additionally performed experiments with two smaller, general-purpose LLMs: Mistral 7B (Jiang et al., 2023), Llama 3 7B (Llama Team, 2024), as well as with one model specially tailored for programming: Code Llama 7B (Rozière et al., 2023).² The results of automatic evaluation are presented in Table 3. It can be ob-

²Corresponding ollama model IDs: mistral, llama3, codellama:7b-instruct.

	BLEU	METEOR
Llama 3 70B	42.51	0.671
Llama 3 7B	39.70	0.670
Mistral 7B	35.36	0.636
Codellama 7B	36.67	0.611

Table 3: Results of automatic evaluation of our rule generation approach using different LLMs on the WebNLG test set using BLEU and METEOR metrics.

served that the task of writing NLG rules is quite challenging for the language models, as there is a significant performance gap, especially in terms of BLEU, between the results of Llama 3 70B and smaller models.

4.3 Human evaluation

To validate the results obtained from automatic metrics, we conducted a small-scale in-house human evaluation. We selected 75 instances from the test set of the WebNLG dataset and evaluated the outputs of our approach and both baselines, totalling 225 system outputs. Following our previous research (Lango and Dusek, 2023), the annotation was performed by asking binary questions related to the existence of minor hallucinations (such as typos in named entity names), major hallucinations (output containing facts not supported by the data), omissions (missing information), disfluencies (grammar errors or difficult-to-read text), and repetitions (information mentioned twice). The annotation was performed by five NLP experts, each output was evaluated by a single annotator. The annotators were shown the input triples along with corresponding outputs from all three evaluated sys-

tems. The annotation process was blinded, with the system outputs order randomly shuffled for each example.

Results The results are presented in Table 2. The proposed rule-based approach produces fewer minor hallucinations than both neural counterparts, has the lowest number of disfluencies and, *ex aequo* with the prompted LLM, the lowest number of repetitions. The model also makes omissions at a frequency comparable to prompted LLM and significantly lower than fine-tuned BART. In terms of major hallucinations, the proposed approach offers a statistically significant improvement over fine-tuned BART³, but falls short of the prompted LLM. We hypothesise that the gap between our system and LLM is a result of error accumulation: our system is partially trained with silver-standard, LLM-generated references that may contain hallucinations, and also suffers from potential errors in the written rules. There is also a possibility that the LLM results on generating outputs from WebNLG dataset are affected by data leakage (Balloccu et al., 2024), which is not the case for generating rules that are not present in the original dataset.

Human intervention experiment Since the manual evaluation identified several hallucinations produced by a rule-based system, we assessed the human effort required to fix them. We randomly selected five examples with hallucinations and asked an experienced Python programmer to fix the code. The programmer was able to use a standard IDE, but without the support of AI tools such as Copilot. The average time to fix one example was three minutes. In the automatic evaluation performed, none of the automatic metrics showed any degradation in the quality of the results, and the results for all selected examples were correct. This demonstrates the interpretability and controllability of the generated rule-based system.

How do the rules look like? The code of a typical rule has 5 lines of code (median) and very often contains renaming or extracting data from the input into a custom data structure (e.g. a dictionary, defaultdict, list) and then filling a textual template. The final text is often constructed by iterating over the input triples or custom data structure and appending parts of the sentence to the output. However, some of the rules are quite complex as

³Confirmed by a two-sample T-test for proportions with continuity correction, with $p = 0.006$.

they list possible conversions of data into text according to the context (e.g. a list how to convert month number into a month name). The code of the longest rule produced has 51 lines. Several examples of written rules are provided in Appendix C.

5 Summary

We presented a new way of training NLG systems for data-to-text problems: we use a large black-box language model to write fully interpretable Python code that is able to generate data textualisation in a fraction of the processing time required by fully neural systems. The experimental evaluation showed that the quality of the generated text is somewhere between that of a few-shot prompted LLM and BART finetuned on the same training data, offering an interesting trade-off between computational and training data requirements, interpretability and predictive performance. In future work, we will extend the synthetic data generation to out-of-domain situations. We also plan to include new types of rules, such as rules operating at the sentence level (e.g. adding subordinate clauses).

Limitations

Currently, our approach does not allow the generation of rules for unseen, i.e. out-of-domain predicates. This could be circumvented by providing a list of out-of-domain relations or even examples of out-of-domain inputs (without reference texts) to our clustering mechanism (Sec. 3.2). Alternatively, these procedures could be applied on-the-fly, but this would require access to an LLM during inference.

The presented approach may also generate hallucinated (i.e. non-factual) outputs, but the experiments demonstrated that the number of hallucinations is smaller than in the text generated by a fine-tuned transformer-based language model.

Supplementary Materials Availability Statement

Source code is available in our GitHub repository.⁴ All experiments were performed on the version of WebNLG dataset available through the HuggingFace Hub.⁵

⁴<https://github.com/jwarczynski/RuLLeM>

⁵https://huggingface.co/datasets/webnl-g-challenge/web_nlg

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A Prompts

In Figures 2, 3 and 4, we provide templates of prompts used in our approach for training a rule-based system.

In Figure 5, we show the prompt used for the zero-shot prompted LLM baseline to generate triple verbalizations directly.

All prompts are templates, with placeholders containing the specific data instances denoted by “{name}”, i.e. they follow the Python string formatting convention.

B Hyperparameters of BART fine-tuning

We used the BART-base model provided by the HuggingFace library.⁶ AdamW with learning rate $\eta = 2 \cdot 10^{-5}$ and parameters $\beta = (0.9, 0.997)$, $\epsilon = 10^{-9}$ was used as optimizer. Additionally, we applied polynomial scheduler of η with a warmup equal to 10% of optimization steps. The training was scheduled for 20 epochs with early stopping on validation loss (patience of 10 epochs). We used batch size equal to 8 and label smoothing with 0.1 smoothing factor.

C Examples of constructed rules

In Figure 6, we provide several examples of rules constructed by our approach.

⁶<https://huggingface.co/facebook/bart-base>

```

Complete Python code to convert given facts (triples) into a factual textual
description (output).
Write only a fragment of Python code that will replace the comment in the snippet
below and nothing else. Do not include code that I have already written. triples
is a list of tuples where each tuple is (subj, relation, obj).
Your code should be included inside this template:

triples = {triples}
relations = [triple.pred for triple in triples]
if (relations == {relations}):
    // your code to generate output
    output = ...
    print(output)

The output should be "{output}". The code should work even if the values of subj and
obj in the triples are different, but the relations (pred) at the input of the
program will always be the same and in the same order. Wrap any code in <code></
code> tags.

```

Figure 2: Prompt used to generate rules in our approach.

```

The desired output is: "{}"
but your code yields: "{}"
Could you produce code that returns the correct output? Remember to wrap the code in
<code></code> tags.

```

Figure 3: Prompt used to inquire for rule edits in our approach.

```

Your task is to create a sample for data-to-text dataset.
For a given set of relations generate a corresponding list of RDF triples and a text
that describes them. Keep the same formatting as in the example below.
All the triples should be related (e.g. add information about already mentioned
entities).
The output text should ONLY describe the input triples and NOT add any extra
information.

#### Example
relations: birth place, birth year, capital of
<sample>
in: (Mozart | birth place | Viena), (Mozart | birth year | 1756), (Vienna | capital
of | Austria)
out: Mozart was born in 1756 in the capital of Austria, Vienna.
</sample>

#### Example
relations: {relations}
<sample>
in: {input}
out: {out}
</sample>

```

Figure 4: Prompt used to generate artificial training instances in our approach.

```

You are given the following list of RDF triples.
{triples}
Write a plain text description of this data. Output only the text of the description
.

```

Figure 5: Prompt for the zero-shot prompted LLM direct data-to-text generation baseline.

```

subj = triples[0].subj
obj = triples[0].obj
relation = triples[0].pred
output = f"{subj} {relation} {obj}."

```

(a) A simple rule to describe the “is part of” relation.

```

subj = triples[0][0]
birth_date = next(obj for subj, pred, obj in triples if pred == 'birth date')
birth_place = next(obj for subj, pred, obj in triples if pred == 'birth place')
alma_mater = next(obj for subj, pred, obj in triples if pred == 'alma mater')
award = next(obj for subj, pred, obj in triples if pred == 'award')

output = f"{subj}, born on {birth_date} in {birth_place}, graduated from {alma_mater}
, his alma mater. He won the prestigious {award}."

```

(b) A rule for describing an input with the following set of relations: “alma mater”, “award”, “birth date” and “birth place”.

```

subj = triples[0].subj
output = f"{triples[1].obj} is the {triples[1].pred} of {subj} located at {float(
triples[2].obj):.0f} metres above sea level in {triples[0].obj}. The airport
runway, named {triples[3].obj} has a length of {float(triples[4].obj):.0f}."

```

(c) A rule for describing an input with the following set of relations: “city served”, “operating organisation”, “elevation above the sea level”, “runway name” and “runway length”. Note the use of number formatting functions.

```

subj = triples[0].subj
industry_obj = [triple.obj for triple in triples if triple.pred == 'industry'][0]
product_obj = [triple.obj for triple in triples if triple.pred == 'product'][0]

if product_obj.lower() == 'world wide web':
    product_obj = 'web'

output = f"{subj} not only offers applications in the {industry_obj.lower()}
industry, but also produces {product_obj} services."

```

(d) A rule for describing an input with the following set of relations: “industry”, “product”. The rule overfitted to the training example related to web applications.

Figure 6: Examples of rules automatically constructed by our approach. Note that by default, the input is accessible to the rules via the “triples” list.